

THE ROLE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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Abstract. *In this article, we will examine the key aspects of using artificial intelligence in teaching English. Artificial intelligence has become an integral part of the modern educational process and significantly impacts the learning of foreign languages, including English. Artificial intelligence technology has significantly developed in recent years, opening up new opportunities for English language learners.*

Keywords: *modern approach, artificial intelligence, training, Duolingo and Babbel platforms, English language.*

Аннотация. *В данной статье мы рассмотрим ключевые аспекты использования искусственного интеллекта в обучении английскому языку. Искусственный интеллект стал неотъемлемой частью современного образовательного процесса и значительно влияет на изучение иностранных языков, включая английский. Технологии искусственного интеллекта значительно развились в последние годы, открывая новые возможности для изучающих английский язык.*

Ключевые слова: *современный подход, искусственный интеллект, обучение, платформы Duolingo и Babbel, английский язык.*

With the advent and development of the World Wide Web, all spheres of human life began to improve. At the same time, the development of the Internet has made it possible to greatly simplify the process of obtaining education for representatives of all segments of the population of our planet. Thus, the development of digital technologies has ensured the availability of education [7]. Digital education, also known as e-learning, refers to the use of digital technologies to provide educational content and provide more learning opportunities [5].

The fastest growing area in the world is digital technology. Every day in the world new details of the digital sphere are being improved and developed, every minute more and more innovative technologies are being introduced in all corners of the world.

In world practice, great attention is paid to teaching foreign languages, where many digital innovative technologies are used. These tools and resources help to improve the learning experience by making it more personalized, interactive, fun, and effective.

With the advent of digital technologies and artificial intelligence, traditional language learning has come into question and integration with digital technologies has become necessary. This is stated in the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On measures for further development of the higher education system” [1]. In turn, learning foreign languages is an important aspect of education in Uzbekistan.

One of the important approaches and advantages when teaching English is personalized learning. The use of artificial intelligence in the educational process makes it possible to create personalized educational programs. Artificial intelligence-based systems can analyze the level of knowledge and pace of learning of each student, allowing materials and assignments to be tailored to individual needs. This helps students learn the language faster and cope with difficulties. Examples of such systems are platforms such as Duolingo and Babbel, which use Artificial intelligence algorithms to track user progress and provide adaptive assignments [3].

There are also interactive assistants, chatbots, and virtual assistants that have been developed using artificial intelligence Artificial intelligence technologies. These assistants can be excellent resources for learning English. They can conduct dialogues, answer questions, and provide additional study materials. For example, chatbots can help students improve their conversational skills by practicing with them, correcting mistakes, and providing recommendations for improving specific skills.

Systems such as Replika and ChatGPT demonstrate how artificial intelligence can be used to create interactive language practice [6].

Another important area of application of artificial intelligence in English language teaching is the automated evaluation of written papers and the provision of feedback. Natural language processing algorithms can analyze texts, identify grammatical errors, suggest improvements, and even assess language proficiency.

Platforms such as Grammarly and ProWritingAid use artificial intelligence to improve writing, offering users tips on style, grammar and vocabulary [4]. We can assume that teachers of our Republic of Uzbekistan also use these platforms in English lessons.

Artificial intelligence also facilitates access to educational resources. Artificial intelligence-based systems can recommend books, articles, videos, and other materials that match the student's interests and level of knowledge. This allows students to find the most appropriate resources for learning the language.

Platforms such as Coursera and edX use artificial intelligence to generate personalized recommendations for courses and materials [2].

Artificial intelligence opens up new horizons in English language teaching, offering innovative approaches that make the learning process more effective and exciting. Personalized learning, interactive assistants, automated assessment and access to a variety of resources all contribute to improving language skills. In the future, we can expect further development of artificial intelligence technologies, which will certainly have an impact on methods and approaches in teaching foreign languages.

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